

soluble in comparison to II. The formation of III is a reversible reaction⁹. Therefore during heating in presence of base III is reversed to II. *p*-Chloroaniline then attacks at C-3 as a nucleophile. The intermediate so formed expels aniline to yield V (Scheme I).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer. The mass spectrum was scanned on a Perkin-Elmer Hitachi RMU-6E Mass spectrometer at 70 eV fitted with a direct inlet system. Thin-layer chromatography was done in benzenemethanol (9:1).

3-(4'-Chlorophenylimino)-2-Indolinone¹(V) :

From I—Isatin (I) (1.47 g ; 0.01 mole), 4-Chloroaniline (1.28 g ; 0.01 mole) and ethanol (25 ml) containing one drop of glacial acetic acid were refluxed for 3 hr. The contents were cooled and the product thus separated was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 257° (Lit¹. m.p. 256-57°), yield 80%.

From III—A mixture of III (2.5 g ; 0.01 mole) ethanol (25 ml) and 4-chloroaniline (1.28 g) was refluxed for 5 min. The product thus obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 257° yield 60%.

From II—A mixture of II (2.22 g ; 0.01 mole), formalin (1 ml) and 4-chloroaniline (1.28 g ; 0.01 mole) was heated at 100° for 5 min. and then allowed to remain at room temp. overnight. The product was recrystallised from ethanol m.p. 257°, yield 55%.

1-Piperidinomethyl-3-(4'-Chlorophenylimino)-2-Indolinone⁵(VI) :

A mixture of V (2.56 g), ethanol (15 ml), formalin (1 ml) and piperidine (0.85 g ; 0.01 mole) was heated for 5 min. at 80°. VI thus separated was filtered, washed with petroleum-ether (b.p. 60-80°) and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 157° (Lit⁵. m.p. 157-58°), yield 60%.

1-Morpholinomethyl-3-(4'-Chlorophenylimino)-2-Indolinone⁵(VII) :

This compound was prepared by taking morpholine instead of piperidine and adopting the procedure described for VI, m.p. 157-58° (Lit⁵. m.p. 158-59°), yield 60%.

1-Hydroxymethyl-3-Phenylimino-2-Indolinone (III) :

A mixture of II (3 g), formalin (5 ml) and water (30 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. The product obtained after allowing the reaction mixture to remain at room temp. overnight, was recrystallised from ethanol m.p. 157-58°, (Lit⁹. m.p. 159-60°), yield 50%.

Reaction of III with *p*-Nitroaniline—III (2.50 g) and *p*-nitroaniline (1.38 g) were taken in 25 ml of

ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min. The product obtained on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 225-26°. It was identical in every respect with II (m.p., m.m.p. and I.R.). Similar reaction of III with *p*-toluidine and *p*-carbomethoxy, *p*-carbomethoxy anilines yielded II.

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Chemical Investigation of Some Mangrove Species Part V : *Phoenix paludosa*

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PHOENIX *palludosa* (Fam. Palmae) occurs in muddy maritime swamp (8-25 ft) has been undertaken for investigation in course of chemotaxonomic studies on Sundarban mangrove. Literature survey on the genus *Phoenix* revealed the distribution of Carotenoids in *P. dactylifera*¹⁻³. Other species of the genus *Phoenix* remained unexplored.

The neutral ether soluble part of the whole plant of *P. paludosa* (3.5 Kg) on chromatography over silica gel G furnished, friedelin (0.02 g), m.p. 248°, [α]_D 71°, β -amyrone (0.2 g) m.p. 168°, [α]_D +117°, triacontanol (0.5 g), m.p. 80° and β -sitosterol (3.0 g), m.p. 138°, [α]_D -35°. Salient features of chromatographic separation are described below.

First eluate registered two intense spot on tlc study. These two compounds could not be separated

by usual recrystallisation procedure. Finally preparative tlc method was adopted to get two homogeneous constituents A and B. The compound A was identical with friedelin as seen by Co-tlc and by Co-glc study. (Ret time 9.5 mins at 278° column: 3% SE 30 on gas chrom-Z, 60-80 mesh.) The second compound B had m.p. 168°. The mixed melting point and the super-impossible IR spectrum showed its identity with β -amyrene.

The fraction from next eluate was triacontanol. The last fraction was β -sitosterol. The amount of β -sitosterol isolated was exceptionally quite large in amount.

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Chemical Constituents of *Ligustrum nelgherrense* Dalz and Gibs var. *obovata**

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LIGUSTRUM nelgherrense Dalz and Gibs var. *obovata* (Oleaceae) grows extensively as a shrub or small tree in the Western peninsula on the Ghats from Bombay southwards to the higher hills of the Konkan and is very common on the Mahabaleshwar plateau.

Under the programme of screening Indian plants over a wide range of biological activity at this Institute it was found that 50 per cent EtOH extract of the whole plant showed anticancer activity¹. The presence of stigmasterol in its roots was reported earlier². The present communication describes the isolation and identification of kaempferitrin, taraxerol, β -sitosterol and β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol from the whole plant in yields ranging from 0.01 to 0.05 per cent.

The alcoholic extract (90-95 per cent) of the air dried whole plant was successively fractionated into benzene, ethylacetate and butanol soluble and aqueous fractions. The ethylacetate and butanol soluble fractions showed marginal activity against P₃₈₈

Lymphocytic leukaemia in mice and were further studied. The butanol soluble fraction on repeated column chromatography over silica gel yielded kaempferitrin³ (I) (3,7-dirhamnosyl kaempferol), C₂₇H₃₀O₄, m.p. 218-20° in 0.01 per cent yield, from the ethylacetate methanol eluted fractions, crystallising as pale yellow needles from methanol. It responded to Shinoda test for flavonoids. The UV spectra showed $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 264 and 345 nm, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH} + \text{AlCl}_3}$ 273, 298 and 374 nm (indicating the presence of a free C-5 hydroxyl group). On acid hydrolysis I yielded kaempferol, m.p. 270-72° (dec.) (lit m.p. 273-75°) and two moles of rhamnose. The observed difference in the m.p. 218-20° (lit³ m.p. 202-203°) of (I) may be attributed to the solvent used for crystallisation⁴. The identity was further supported by its NMR spectrum at 90 MHz in DMSO-d₆. The signals due to two methyl protons of the two rhamnose units attached at C-3 and C-7 in I, appeared as doublets at 85 and 112 cps (J, 6.5 Hz). The glycosyl protons in turn appeared at 530 and 553 cps. The other protons of the rhamnose molecules crowded as broad peaks between 300 to 425 cps. The protons of the aromatic nuclei of the flavonol moiety could be assigned as follows: The protons at C-6 and C-8 showing *meta* coupling, appeared at 645 and 675 cps respectively as narrow doublets (J, 2Hz). The two doublets of two protons each at 690 and 780 cps (J, 10Hz) may be assigned to 3', 5' and 2', 6' protons respectively showing *ortho* couplings.

The ethylacetate soluble fraction on chromatography separately over silica gel column using benzene, benzene-ethylacetate mixture as eluents afforded colourless needles of taraxerol, m.p. 278-80°, C₃₀H₅₀O, crystallising from methanol; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH group); acetate C₃₂H₅₂O₂, m.p. 302-304° (m. mp and superimposable IR spectra with that of an authentic sample). Further elution of the column with ethyl acetate and ethylacetate-methanol mixture yielded a sterol glycoside, m.p. 292-96° (d), C₃₅H₅₈O₆ in 0.02 per cent yield and crystallising as microcrystalline needles from methanol. On acid hydrolysis it gave one mole each of β -sitosterol and glucose. Its identity as β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol was confirmed by m. mp and superposable IR spectra. The earlier fractions eluted with benzene afforded in poor yields free β -sitosterol as well.

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